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A HEALTHCARE INSTITUTION MANAGER'S DEONTOLOGICAL CULTURE AS A COMPONENT OF THE PROFESSIONAL IMAGE

ДЕОНТОЛОГІЧНА КУЛЬТУРА КЕРІВНИКА ЗАКЛАДУ ОХОРОНИ ЗДОРОВ'Я ЯК СКЛАДОВА ЙОГО ПРОФЕСІЙНОГО ІМІДЖУ

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Балан О.С., Шепель М.Є., Савеліч Л.В. Деонтологічна культура керівника закладу охорони здоров'я як складова його професійного іміджу. Науково-методична стаття.

Стаття присвячена деонтологічній культурі керівника закладу охорони здоров'я як одному з компонентів його професійного іміджу. Зазначено, що у науково-методичній літературі представлено розгалужені уявлення вчених щодо питань деонтологічної культури, іміджу, професійної культури та професійної етики. Метою статті виступило визначити взаємовідношення деонтологічної культури та професійного іміджу керівника закладу охорони здоров'я. Визначено, що професійний імідж є комплексним поняттям. Професійний імідж та деонтологічна культура взаємопов'язані, адже базуються на моральних та етичних принципах. Складовими професійного іміджу з позиції деонтології визначено культуру спілкування, корпоративну культуру, командна робота, лідерські якості, вміння вирішувати конфлікти. На основі дослідженої літератури авторами запропоновано модель удосконалення деонтологічної культури як складової іміджу керівника закладу охорони здоров'я. Імплементация даної моделі вбачається через поради, круглі столи, тренінги та вебінари з запрошеними фахівцям, дискусії.

Ключові слова: деонтологія, деонтологічна культура, імідж, професійний імідж, керівник, заклад охорони здоров'я

Balan O.S., Shepel M.Ye., Savelich L.V. A Healthcare Institution Manager's Deontological Culture as a Component of the Professional Image. Scientific and methodical article.

The article deals with the healthcare institution manager's deontological culture as one of the components of the professional image. It has been emphasized that the scientific and methodological literature presents scientists' extensive ideas regarding the issues of deontological culture, image, professional culture, and professional ethics. The aim of the article was to determine the relationship between the healthcare institution manager's deontological culture and the professional image. Professional image and deontological culture are interconnected because they are based on moral and ethical principles. The components of a professional image from the standpoint of deontology have been defined as the communication culture, corporate culture, teamwork, leadership qualities, conflict resolution skills. This model implementation is seen through pieces of advice, round tables, workshops and webinars with invited professionals, and discussions.

Keywords: deontology, deontological culture, image, professional image, a manager, a healthcare institution

The Russian Federation's invasion into the territory of the independent, sovereign, and democratic Ukraine has drastically changed the Ukrainian people's life. In today's conditions, not only a combat-ready army but also the Ukrainian nation's health preservation have become important. The health-preserving factor should be present more than ever in all areas of activity, both medical and educational, military, industrial and other. It is healthcare institutions that must implement the state policy regarding the nation's health preservation. It is known that the basic concepts of building a healthcare system are defined in Article 4 of the Law of Ukraine "Basics of The Legislation of Ukraine on Healthcare" [1]. Great importance in healthcare institutions' administration is played by their managers. The level of a healthcare institution manager's deontological culture, which is a component of the professional image, becomes important.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Both Ukrainian and foreign scholars dedicated their works to professional culture and image: O. Malyshevskiy, Yu. Hvozdetzka, L. Filshtein, V. Zhuravlov, D. Kirch, V. Zaitseva, N. Yaremchuk, Yu.S. Hrebenyk, Yu. Orel-Khalik, M. Demianchuk, V. Hrynova, S. Makarenko, O. Lytvynova, N. Abashnyk, T.D. Shanafelt, E. Shein, L.B. Mainor, M. Trokel, P. Shein, H. Naumenko, N. Barna, L. Danylchuk, I. Koloskova, S. Kolosok, Yu. Padafet, O. Haivoronska, O. Kapustyk, I. Krynitskiy, O. Myttseva, H. Popova, L. Serheieva, S. Konvei, L. Dobelli, Dzh. Khike, O. Loshenko, I. Hrytsenko,

V. Savishchenko, O. Huzhva. Such scientists as R.-S. Balica, O. Braktova, T. Galkina, N. Nikitina, V. Sizikova, D. Chemodonova, V. Grebennikova, Ye. Hida, S. Hlyestova, I. Kaminska, A. Matviichuk, I. Starovoi, O. Bepalova, Yu. Kurnyshev, A. Sitovskiy, I.V. Savchuk, E. Kosynskiy, A. Tymchenko devoted their research papers to specialists' deontological culture I. Bostan, C. Costuleanu, E. Horomnea, M. Costuleanu, C.L. Donoho, M.J. Polonsky, S. Roberts, D.A. Cohen, E. Kaynak, N. Delener, O. Lapuzina, R.J. Major, B. Menguc, V.B. Nunes & L.L. de Souza, D. Probucka, N.Y.M. Siu, K.C.J. Lam, A.A. Vásquez-Párraga & A. Kara considered specialists' professional ethics in their studies.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

The conducted analysis of reference literature shows that scientists haven't paid much attention to the healthcare institution manager's deontological culture as a part of the professional image.

The aim of the article is to emphasize the correlation between the healthcare institution manager's deontological culture and the professional image.

The main part

Deontology is usually interpreted as the ethics of duty. The basis for this distinction is the various means of declaring one's position in the form of imperatives expressing obligation or prohibition, and as assessment that implies approval or condemnation. Deontology denies the need to consider the motives, goals, and consequences of an act in order to qualify it as moral in general since the moral specificity of the act is determined not by what it is performed for, but by an impulse, a sense of obligation [2].

Deontology is associated with the following features which play a more or less significant role in different deontological theories: agent-relativity, especially agent-relative constraints (restrictions), options (prerogatives) and special obligations; priority of the right over the good; definition of the right independently of the good; priority of honoring values over promoting values; intrinsically wrong actions; absolutely wrong actions and exceptionless moral rules; duty for duty's sake; pluralism of moral rules; respect of persons; non-instrumentalization of persons; human dignity; inviolable rights [3].

Today, deontology is a widely used social concept. Considering the evolutionary path of this term formation, it is necessary to remember that "deontology" is derived from the Greek "deontos" which means "duty" and "logos" which means "teaching". The definition of the concept of "deontology" as a scientific term belongs to the English philosopher, sociologist, and jurist Jeremy Bentham, who in his book "Deontology, or The Science of Morality" (1834) interpreted it as "the science of obligatory and proper" to denote the teaching of moral values in general [4].

For a long time, in the narrow sense, deontology was understood as only healthcare workers' professional ethics, which included the appropriate

system of ethical norms of behaviour that regulates their professional activities implementation [5].

I. Starovoi considers deontology as a living ontology, an ontology in action. The scientist states that "it is important for it to move its mind towards the future, to the action, to the right and proper. For the latter, the most characteristic is a person's attitude of to the reality... Deontology scientifically substantiates the need for conscious subordination of personal interests to the social needs in a harmonious combination of personal and public, determines the forms of professional morality civic duty, fulfillment in a specific field of public: life and activity" [6].

Professional deontology is a complex entity that contains various fields of knowledge about moral and ethical duty in professions with a high degree of responsibility: doctor, teacher, psychologist, scientist, lawyer, military, civil servant, etc. Such professions are focused on ensuring fundamental values: life, health, peace, security, justice, freedom, dignity, goodness, future. The common subject of professional deontology research connects its various branches: medical, legal, pedagogical, psychological, deontology of public service, and deontology of scientific activity:

- moral and ethical content of professional duty and responsibility;
- external professional ethical standards of behaviour, i.e. norms of interaction with people who need professional services, their relatives, etc.;
- corporate ethical standards of behaviour, i.e. norms of interaction in a professional environment;
- professional restrictions and prohibitions, norms of behaviour outside the performance of professional functions [7].

As our research is devoted to epy healthcare institution manager's deontological culture we should take into account that according to Order No. 1977 of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine was issued on 31 October 2018, which provided that from 1 January 2019 in Ukraine, a director and medical director's functions in medical institutions will be clearly demarcated: the director of the institution deals with economic activity issues, and the medical director deals with exclusively medical issues [8]. According to this order a healthcare institution manager can be a person with medical education and with no medical education, but with education in public administration.

Investigating a medical specialist's deontological culture, L. Pereimybida notes that the deontological culture is a degree of a medical specialist's fulfillment of his/her duties to society; moral and psychological readiness for professional activity; development degree of a personality's motional-volitional sphere and intersocial abilities [9].

S. Hlyestova defines the deontological culture as one of the most important components of a person's professional culture. A student's deontological culture is considered as a set of the personality's spiritual and intellectual, emotional-value, and professional ethical

qualities that determine the ethical and cultural significance of his/her life [10].

Medical deontology has taken on the ideas of patient information and informed consent. This has been a long process which has brought considerable changes to the deontological orientations of the traditional form of doctor-patient relationship. In these aspects, medical deontology has drifted, from emphasizing the prudence of the doctor, to emphasize the duty to inform and give ample space to the patient's decisions, which he recognizes as an autonomous and reflective moral agent, capable of taking his own decisions about health [11].

At the international and national levels, a number of normative documents have been developed and implemented, which outline ethical principles, moral principles, and norms of behaviour of a medical worker in the performance of professional duties. At the same time, socio-economic changes, the rapid development of medicine, the healthcare system and medical education reformation, the desire to get closer to European standards, introducing new models of providing medical services necessitate professional competences improvement in the medical field, especially under conditions of significant professional competition on the labour market. Considering that deontological competence is an integral part of professional competences, in many aspects determining the professional level of specialists in the field of healthcare, issues related to the improvement of the relevant legal framework and the process of forming a system of deontological knowledge, skills and abilities, are becoming more and more relevant and need immediate solutions [12].

Therefore, deontological culture is closely related to professional ethics, which is part of the professional's image.

Ethical formation, as V. Nunes and L.L. de Sousa mention, is comprehended as the one that accomplishes itself in a planned and organized way and aims the critical thinking about and in the concrete moral action, being possible for all people [13].

Investigating the correlation between social responsibility and ethics N. Delener and E. Kayanak highlight that knowledge of consumers' perceptions of ethical behaviour could provide managers with valuable insight for the design and administration of a company's marketing and channel strategies, staff policies and corporate image [14].

N.Y.M. Siu and K.C.J. Lam compare managers and non-managers' ethical perceptions, including professionals, teachers, sales persons, clerks, technical and plant workers, and emphasize that managers tend to possess deontological views that are more ethical than that found in other occupations. The gap between managers and other professionals in perceiving unethical behaviour is narrower compared to that between the former and individuals in other occupations [15].

Distinguishing ethics and deontology R.-S. Balica states that ethics is the science that deals with moral principles, representing the set of norms and rules of

moral behaviour, about the ideology of a class or society. Deontology is a behaviour of ethics, that has the power to impose, while a deontological code involves a set of strict norms and rules that must be respected by those who practice a particular profession, so doctors, lawyers, journalists carry out their work on the basis of such a code [16].

R.J. Major distinguishes virtue ethics from consequentialist and deontological ethics. The scientist identifies two dynamics of exemplarity: on the one hand, collective, normed mimetic processes that facilitate socialization, cultural assimilation, and the transmission of knowledge and skills. On the other hand, individuals are sources of inspiration, appealing to what is best within human beings, encouraging agents to become better associates, better managers, and better people [17].

O. Bratkova notes that «professional ethics is first and foremost a specific code of ethics for people of a particular profession. Each profession imposes appropriate moral requirements to the people who have chosen it, and it creates special moral problems» [18]. The scientist highlights the basic moral and ethical norms that promote effective professional interaction and communication: integrity, honesty, objectivity, tolerance, respect, responsibility, etc. [18].

As it has been mentioned above ethics influences a person's professional image.

The definitions of the concept of "image" state that the image contains not only an individual's natural properties, but also specially designed, created, and formed ones. In other definitions, it is emphasized that the image is largely determined by the objective characteristics of the object, in particular, a person's image is determined by the psychological type and compliance with the demands of time and society. Many image professionals include in this phenomenon not only the person's appearance, which is created due to the anatomical features and clothing style, but also almost all characteristics accessible to perception [19].

It is known that image belongs to the group of socio-psychological phenomena. Thus, it obeys all the basic laws of social psychology. Let's consider them in the form of Figure 1.

Until 1992, the term "image" was not used in domestic professional language practice, which led to its simplified perception and the uncertainty of the scientific apparatus. L. Danylchuk states that the concept of "image" is a complete, clearly defined, stable and updated image of an object in mass and/or individual consciousness, which is created to transform it into society [20].

A professional's image has the character of a stereotype, that is, a simplified, non-multifaceted image. It should not have a large number of characteristics. Its research should be carried out for a scheme with a limited number of components:

- manifestations of the professional's personal traits and characteristics;
- behaviour and nature of relations in the workforce;
- the results of professional activity [21].

Figure 1. Laws of Social Psychology
Source: compiled by authors on materials [24]

So, we can say that professional image/ the professional's image is an idea about an individual as a representative of a certain profession. It is the impression created around a specific person in order to popularize him as a professional, and to exert an emotional and psychological influence on other people's opinions (management, colleagues, partners). Professional image and the professional's image are synonyms.

Deontological culture as a part of professional image is connected with speech culture (communication skills) corporate culture, teamwork, and leadership skills. All these skills are based on the professional's morality.

Communication culture depends on mastering knowledge, norms, qualities, and rules. Communication effectiveness is also ensured by the internal need to realize the individuality and uniqueness of the subject, tolerance, tact, politeness, showing sincere interest and respect for the interlocutor, the ability to control gestures and facial expressions, one's own behaviour and that of the recipient, and the desire for emotional and intellectual interaction [22].

Speech culture is considered as a tool for self-realization of the individual in contacts with other people, a behavioural strategy in interpersonal communication [23].

In communication culture, some aspects of speech become important. Thus, the meaningfulness of speech implies the necessary degree of brevity, the absence of empty phrases and verbiage, compliance

with the literary language norms, the rules of emphasis, the rules of pronunciation, the rules of word usage, the rules of creating grammatical forms and combinations of words and combining them into sentences. Speech accuracy is the ability to select from a rich vocabulary such as language units and forms that would ensure the achievement of communication goal. Speech fluency is the accuracy of expression of thoughts, feelings, and expressions of will with the help of precisely chosen words and constructions of sentences, the correct division of the statement with the help of logical pauses into meaningful parts, the appropriate arrangement of logical accents. As a rule, the speaker acts as the communication initiator. He/she programmes the course of the conversation and predicts the listener's speech actions. Clarity of speech presupposes the correspondence of the expression plan to the content plan in the form in which it has been formed in the mind of the speaker, is not only a communicative quality, but also an expressive one, which plays a leading role in the process of one's opinion formation [24].

Communication, as a rule, takes place in the form of dialogue, conversation, which, in turn, includes deontological principles. The healthcare institution manager conducts a conversation, dialogue with colleagues, subordinate patients. Let's consider the structural components complex of dialogue culture, which for better clarity is presented in the form of Table 1.

Table 1. The Structural Components of the Dialogue Culture

Component	Criteria
intellectual and cognitive	knowledge about people's psychological characteristics, the ability to substantiate one's own opinions, to analyze a dialogic situation, to make decisions
motivational and valuable	the need for dialogical communication, the desire to exchange information, understanding the value of subject-subject relations
moral and spiritual	conscious attraction to spiritual enrichment, openness to moral and spiritual communication, humane attitude to the interlocutor
emotional and volitional	ability to empathic and tolerant behaviour, self-control and absence of aggression; operational-activity (defined by self-realization, initiative in dialogue, cooperation in the opinion development, expedient behaviour in different communicative situations)
language and speech	the ability to formulate one's own viewpoint without mistake, possession of linguistic etiquette, vocabulary, adequacy of expression

Source: compiled by authors on materials [24]

The next important aspect is corporate culture as a component of professional culture and image. Corporate culture in the system of human resources management of the institution is considered as a strategic tool, which allows to orient all its subdivisions and all employees for general purposes, to increase personnel initiative, to provide loyalty to the general business, to facilitate communication. Corporate culture is a part of the country's culture of the community, in many respects is formed by values that prevail in the mass consciousness. On the basis of old values stereotypes and rules of behaviour are formed, which, in turn, are formed with time in business habits and traditions [25].

Corporate culture can be considered as a kind of management ideology aimed at increasing the organization's business activity in general and its manager in particular. Management ideology is manifested in the organization's mission and goals, and it affects:

- employees' relations with the organization;
- the basic principles of the employees and the organization's activity in general;
- the organization's relations with business partners, competitors, consumers;
- positioning in relation to society;
- general worldview positions.

Management experts argue that leaders create and change cultures, while managers and administrators exist within them. They emphasize that the manager's talent is determined by the ability to understand the meaning of corporate culture and be able to work in it [26]. That is, in our opinion, in order to maintain a professional culture and a stable positive image, the healthcare institution manager needs to be more of an administrator than a leader.

The organizational corporate culture is a system of collectively shared values, beliefs, traditions, and norms of employees' behaviour. It is expressed in the symbolic means of the spiritual and material environment of people who work in this organization [26]. That is, corporate culture is based on deontological principles: the manager's and subordinates' moral principles

The ability to work in a team, i.e. teamwork skills, plays an important role in the healthcare institution manager's professional image from the position of deontology. Teamwork is considered as the ability of a group of people to work well together [27]. Teamwork skills are qualities and abilities that allow

the professional to work well with others during conversations, projects, meetings, or other collaborations. Teamwork skills depend on the professional's ability to communicate well, actively listen, be responsible and honest [28].

Leadership is a management relationship between a leader and followers, which is based on an effective combination of various sources of power for a given situation and is aimed at motivating people to achieve common goals [29].

It is well known that some personal qualities influence the leadership effectiveness. The need for them is determined by the situation specifics and the tasks specifics. In this case, a combination of personal traits with professional competence is necessary. An effective leader must be able to: carry out a strategic outline of the development prospects of the managed organization; simulate a complex situation; calculate the risk; to change the organizational structure and culture [30].

An effective leader's characteristics of can be distinguished, which can be considered from the viewpoint of deontology: features of thinking (the ability to extrapolate; the ability to develop several problems at the same time; stability in a situation of uncertainty; understanding, developed intuition, the ability to grasp the essence of the matter intuitively and quickly); ability to cope with aggression (ability to take control; persistence; ability to cooperate; initiative; energy); management of emotions (ability to bet on others, sensitivity, self-identification with the cause, ability to empathize, interest in the group members' "growth", independence); personal ideal (flexibility, stress resistance, presence of a goal, sense of humor, integrity of personal ideal) [31].

Conflict resolution is also based on morality, which is a component of deontological culture. Different types of conflicts can occur in the workplace [32]:

- conflict may arise between colleagues at work, or between managers and subordinates, or between service providers and their clients or customers.
- conflict can also occur between groups, such as management and the workforce, or between entire units.

So, as it can be seen, professional image from the standpoint of deontological culture: communication culture, leadership skills, teamwork skills, conflict resolution skills.

Figure 2 The Model of Improving Deontological Culture as a Component of the Healthcare Institution Manager's Professional Image.

Source: authors' own development

In order to improve the deontological culture as a component of the healthcare institution manager’s professional image, we offer the following model, which we will display in the form of Figure 2.

Analyzing, Figure 2, we see that the aim of the model is to improve the deontological culture as a component the healthcare institution manager’s professional image. At the same time, professional image is a broad term, and it is necessary to highlight components of professional image from the standpoint of deontology: communication culture, corporate culture, teamwork skills, leadership skills, conflict resolution skills. These components can be developed through seminars, webinars, trainings, debates, advice, round tables.

We will give recommendations for improving deontological culture as a component of the healthcare institution manager’s professional image.

We will provide the following tips for the development of communicative culture skills:

- establishing contact with the interlocutor: demonstrating interest and willingness to talk to the interlocutor through facial expression and body position;
- active listening: to give the interlocutor signals that he/she is listened carefully and is tried to be understood. In order to do this, from time to time you can repeat in your own words the most important statements of the interlocutor, use positive or questioning intonation, make short remarks such as: "Yes, I see", "Exactly", "Interesting", "Great";

- be observant, carefully monitor the interlocutor’s emotions and mood;
- do not interrupt the interlocutor, giving him the opportunity to express his/her opinion to the end;
- so that the interlocutor correctly understands the main idea, do not get carried away with general words or too long phrases;
- speak loud and clear enough (this adds confidence to the speech);
- maintain eye contact with the interlocutor, using adequate non-verbal signals (gestures, movements, facial expressions, mimicry, etc.).

Since corporate culture and teamwork are interconnected, in our opinion, it is advisable for the healthcare institution manager to use exercises aimed at teambuilding: joint work on a project, joint seminars, round tables within the organization, and weekend guided tours. For the development of corporate culture, the joint creation of the the organization’s corporate code, in this case the healthcare institution, is also of great importance.

It is advisable to improve leadership qualities at personal growth workshops, in some cases it is necessary to contact the coach personally.

In order to develop a leader’s personality, the following trajectory can be used. For greater clarity, we present in the form of Table 2.

Let’s consider Thomas-Kilmann model, which defines five different approaches to conflict resolution. We present the model in the form of Fig 3.

Table 2 The Trajectory of the Leader’s Personality development

Trajectory	Indicators
personality	has a rich moral, cultural and humanistic potential, has the ability to affect people emotionally, is the bearer of a certain culture aimed at harmonizing relationships in the team and cultivates responsibility
leader	has charisma, inspires trust, produces ideas, knows how to convince and unite people around him/her to achieve common goals; ensures development
reformer	possesses strategic thinking; initiates transformative actions capable of modernizing the civil service system; is able to overcome stereotypes, has the ability to provide valid arguments for actions;
facilitator	is able to organize the process of collective problem-solving in his/her team; makes optimal decisions and bears responsibility for them; helps subordinates and promotes teamwork; creates a spirit of solidarity and cooperation
intellectual	possesses the appropriate level of education and professionalism, is able to create an atmosphere of intellectual collegiality, influences people’s minds

Source: compiled by authors on materials [33]

Figure 3 Thomas-Kilmann Model in Resolving conflicts

Source: compiled by authors on materials [34]

Thomas-Kilmann model identifies two dimensions that people fall into when choosing conflict resolution strategies: persistence and cooperation. Assertiveness involves taking action to meet one's own needs, while cooperativeness involves taking action to meet the needs of another.

So, as we can see, deontological culture is an important component of the healthcare institution manager's professional image. Professional image is a complex term itself. It includes the following components from the standpoint of deontology: communication culture, leadership skills, teamwork skills, conflict resolution skills. We can say that professional image and deontological culture are interconnected, as the healthcare institution manager should act on the moral and ethical principles, which are the basis of deontological culture.

Conclusions

In compliance with the recommendations and requirements presented in the article, it is expected to improve the environmental situation as a whole, which will bring in the future a reduction in the cost of combating environmental problems and the stability and growth of the state economy.

Ukraine cannot but take into account that the world economy is moving towards ecological principles, and therefore must build its economic and political strategy.

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Abstract

The Russian Federation's invasion into the territory of the independent, sovereign, and democratic Ukraine has drastically changed the Ukrainian people's life. In today's conditions, not only a combat-ready army but also the Ukrainian nation's health preservation have become important. The health-preserving factor should be present more than ever in all areas of activity, both medical and educational, military, industrial and other. It is healthcare institutions that must implement the state policy regarding the nation's health preservation. It is known that the basic concepts of building a healthcare system are defined in Article 4 of the Law of Ukraine "Basics of the Legislation of Ukraine on Healthcare". Great importance in healthcare institutions administration is played by their managers. The level the healthcare institution manager's deontological culture, which is a component of the professional image, becomes important.

Both Ukrainian and foreign scholars dedicated their works to professional culture and image, deontological culture and professional image.

The conducted analysis of reference literature shows that scientists haven't paid much attention to the healthcare institution manager's deontological culture as a part of their professional image.

The aim of the article is to emphasize the correlation between healthcare institution managers' deontological culture and their professional image.

Deontological culture is an important component of the healthcare institution manager's professional image. The model for improving the healthcare institution manager's deontological culture has been developed. The aim of the model is to improve the deontological culture as a component the healthcare institution manager's professional image. At the same time, professional image is a broad term, and it is necessary to highlight components of professional image from the standpoint of deontology: communication culture, corporate culture, teamwork skills, leadership skills, conflict resolution skills. These components can be developed through seminars, webinars, trainings, debates, advice, round tables.

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